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Inciting a Cognitive Conflict: A Challenge to Students in Introductory Mechanics

B Schmidt¹

Associate Professor
SDU-Mechatronics, University of Southern Denmark
Sønderborg, Denmark
E-mail: bschmidt@mci.sdu.dk

ABSTRACT

The concept of force is a key concept in any pre-university physics course, but nevertheless it is well known that many students face severe problems because of misunderstandings within this subject when enrolled at an engineering program. The direction of the friction force in different settings is one example that often puzzles the students. Using a cylinder pulled by a force on a horizontal surface is a well-suited situation that can be studied at class with or by the students to gain detailed understanding of the forces involved.

In this work-in-progress, we present an extension of the standard treatment of the pulled cylinder found in the literature. We focus on modelling the induced friction force when the cylinder is pulled at different angles to horizontal and letting the pulling force attack at different heights of the cylinder. As a consequence, the analysis leads to several conclusions that we find very useful when teaching introductory mechanics. From previous investigations, we know that these conclusions are counter-intuitive to our first year engineering students, and thus the pulled cylinder may serve as a prime example to create a cognitive conflict at class. As suggested by other authors, inciting a cognitive conflict can be a very fruitful starting point for deep learning.

In addition, we present a setup for a demo experiment that illustrates qualitatively the features of the friction force on the pulled cylinder predicted by the dynamical model. Finally, we discuss different approaches to the topic at class in order to optimize the learning outcome.

Conference Key Areas: Physics and Engineering Education / Engineering Education Research / Engineering Skills

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¹ Corresponding Author
B Schmidt
bschmidt@mci.sdu.dk

INTRODUCTION

There is a range of sources that explains why mechanics is often seen as a difficult subject. Among them are the material being abstract, the necessary precision required, and the intense use of mathematical descriptions within the subject. In this paper, we focus on another source of difficulty, which is the presence in mechanics of inherently difficult *conceptual primitives*. These primitives consist of *specific primitives* (or *key concepts*) like mass, acceleration, force, momentum etc., and *generic primitives* (or *fundamental theories and models*) such as Newton's laws, conservation theorems etc. [1]. Many students struggle with understanding these concepts at a qualitative level, but the difficulties may go undetected in traditional problem solving because the student with superficial knowledge and formula manipulation techniques can mask the misunderstanding of the underlying qualitative concepts [2]. The basic misconceptions are highly resistant to change and as discussed by Clement [2] they are remarkable similar to misconceptions treated as early as in the 17th century by Galileo!

During the past seven years we have used a student response system ("clickers") and peer instruction quite intensively in our introductory mechanics classes. Some of the problems described above become clear when looking at the data gathered by the response system. Of particular interest in this context is a multiple choice question where the students were asked what will happen when a cable reel on a horizontal surface with plenty of friction is pulled by a force as shown in *Fig. 1*.

Fig. 1. Illustration to clicker question: In which direction will the cable reel move?

The students answered the question by themselves anonymously, and after seeing the distribution of answers they discussed in small groups before giving in an answer again. Results for the same question during the five year period 2011-2015 are given in *Fig. 2*. The data has been collected for ten classes with a total number of approximately 350 students. It shows that only a relatively poor number of students have the correct answer, and moreover, the students cannot in general increase the number of correct answers significantly by discussing in groups since most of the data points are close to or below the dotted line in the figure. This is in contrast to a previous study where we found that peer instruction is very likely to improve the students learning outcome, and even in cases where all students have severe difficulties with a certain question the peer discussions might increase the ratio of correct answers to as much as 80% [3]. Hence, pulling a cable reel or a cylinder on a horizontal surface is what González-Espada et al. have called a discrepant event [4]. Such events are powerful possibilities to stimulate interest, motivate students to challenge their misconceptions and promote higher-order thinking skills. When

exposing students to evidence that directly contradicts their ideas a cognitive conflict is created, and this can be utilized in the teaching [5, 6, 7].

Fig. 2 . Percentage of correct answers to cable reel question

Some of the difficulties in the example with the pulled cylinder are due to the relation between force and acceleration, and it has been addressed by a number of authors by studying a rolling cylinder on a horizontal plane. To demonstrate the direction of the friction force on a rolling cylinder Shaw [8] proposed an experiment where he also measured the friction force when the cylinder was pulled at two different heights. A similar, but slightly simpler, setup was described by Salazar et al. [9] where they argued that most students consider the direction of the friction force on a rolling cylinder a paradox. Pinto and Fiolhais [10] have presented a systematic study on the friction force resulting from a horizontal pull at various heights of the cylinder and derived the conditions for the static friction coefficient to ensure rolling with and without slipping. A dynamical model for the rolling cylinder based on the exchange of linear and angular momentum between the rolling body and the underlying surface was described in a paper by D'Anna [11]. In addition, she presented a simple idea to illustrate experimentally the difference in the cylinders interaction with the surface and thus measuring the direction of the friction force.

A common feature in all the work mentioned above is that the cylinder is pulled by a horizontal force only. The angle dependence for a pulled cylinder has been studied by Mungan [12] but with a focus on the acceleration of the cylinder and deriving two critical angles where the cylinder slips on the surface without rolling and rolls without slipping regardless of value of the static friction coefficient. Carvalho and Sousa [13] reported on an interesting study about a number of conceptual problems involved in rotational motion, one of them being the pulled cylinder. They included a brief analysis with conditions for the direction of friction being in one direction or the other and useful comments on teaching approaches as well. In the present paper, we model not only how the friction force depends on the height of the pulling force but also how friction depends on the angle of the pull. In addition, we describe a simple setup for demonstrating the findings.

1 THE DYNAMICAL MODEL

1.1 Free body diagram

We look at a cylinder of radius R on a horizontal surface with sufficient friction to provide rolling without slipping. The cylinder is pulled by a force T at a distance r from the center of gravity G and at an angle θ to horizontal.

Fig. 3. Free body diagram

In addition, we have gravity acting at G and a normal force N and friction F acting at the contact point C .

1.2 Equations of motion

Applying Newton's 2nd law along the x -axis gives

$$\sum F_x = m\bar{a} \Rightarrow T \cos \theta - F = m\bar{a} \Leftrightarrow F = T \cos \theta - m\bar{a} \quad (1)$$

while for motion along the y -axis we find

$$\sum F_y = 0 \Rightarrow N + T \sin \theta - mg = 0 \Leftrightarrow N = mg - T \sin \theta. \quad (2)$$

Since we assume rolling without slipping, Newton's 2nd law for the rotational motion yields

$$\sum M_G = \bar{I}\alpha \Rightarrow -T \cdot r + F \cdot R = \bar{I} \cdot \frac{\bar{a}}{R} \Leftrightarrow \frac{F \cdot R^2}{\bar{I}} - \frac{T \cdot r \cdot R}{\bar{I}} = \bar{a} \quad (3)$$

where \bar{I} is the moment of inertia for the cylinder about the center of gravity.

1.3 The friction force

Substituting Eq. (3) into Eq. (1) gives

$$F = T \cos \theta - \frac{m \cdot F \cdot R^2}{\bar{I}} + \frac{m \cdot T \cdot r \cdot R}{\bar{I}} \quad (4)$$

and solving for the friction force we get

$$F = \frac{T \cos \theta + \frac{m \cdot T \cdot r \cdot R}{\bar{I}}}{1 + \frac{m \cdot R^2}{\bar{I}}} \quad (5)$$

Setting $\bar{I} = \frac{1}{2} m R^2$ (i.e. we use the moment of inertia of a solid cylinder, which is a good model for the experimental demo presented in the next section) this equation reduces to

$$F = \frac{1}{3} T \left(\cos \theta + 2 \frac{r}{R} \right) \quad (6)$$

From Eq. (6) it is easy to determine if the friction force might become zero:

$$F = 0 \Leftrightarrow \cos \theta = -2 \frac{r}{R} \quad (7)$$

where we have neglected the trivial solution $T = 0$.

A graph of the friction force relative to the pulling force, F/T , as given by Eq. (6) has been plotted in Fig. 4. In Fig. 5 we have plotted the implicit function in Eq. (7) and indicated the regions where the friction force is positive and negative, respectively.

Fig. 4. Plot of $\frac{F}{T}(r/R, \theta)$.

Fig. 5. Sign of the friction force depending on the pulling angle θ and the ratio r/R .

1.4 Critical angle

To find the angle θ_c where the cylinder is not moving despite the pull, the acceleration of the center of gravity is set to zero. With $\bar{a} = 0$ Eq. (1) and (3) reduce to

$$F = T \cos \theta_c \quad (8)$$

$$-T \cdot r + F \cdot R = 0 \quad (9)$$

By combining these two equations we find the criterion for the cylinder being at rest even though we are pulling:

$$\cos \theta_c = \frac{r}{R} \quad (10)$$

We note that the critical angle does not depend on the pulling force T . When the cylinder is pulled at the angle θ_c it will remain at rest until the horizontal component of T exceeds the maximum friction $\mu_s N$. By applying Eq. (2) this happens when

$$T > \frac{\mu_s mg}{\cos \theta_c + \mu_s \sin \theta_c} \quad (11)$$

2 EXPERIMENTAL DEMO SETUP

To illustrate the qualitative implications of the model, a fairly simple demo setup has been developed (*Fig. 6*). On top of a rectangular plate of acrylic glass some rubber material has been mounted to ensure plenty of friction from the surface. The plate rests on many small metal spheres allowing the plate to move very smoothly in the surrounding frame. At each end the plate has been connected to the frame by a couple of springs.

Fig. 6. Demo setup to illustrate direction of the friction force

Two wheels have been joined with a smaller cylinder between them. With a mass of the inner cylinder much smaller than the wheels, this makes up a sufficient demo model of an object with the same moment of inertia as a simple cylinder. Obviously, when pulling the wheel, the direction of the friction force can be determined by observing the recoil of the surface.

3 IN THE CLASSROOM

The example with the pulled cylinder can be used in different ways in an introductory mechanics course. What we have found most rewarding is when the students are faced with several cognitive conflicts during the lecture. This can be realized as sketched below. In addition, it is a prime example on how to model dynamics by using the equations of motion.

- Ask the students a (clicker) question as illustrated in *Fig. 1*. When it does not seem to be straight forward let the students discuss the question in small groups.
- Demonstrate (on a fixed surface) that the cylinder will move to the right. Most students will find the answer counter intuitive, and it will stimulate their interest in the setup.
- Let the students establish the free body diagram. Ask them to find the moment of force about the contact point to eliminate the contribution from the unknown friction force. The students will be able to conclude that the cylinder rotates

clockwise and hence move to the right, since only the pulling force is applying a moment of force about C.

- (d) Use the demo setup to illustrate the direction of the friction force in this situation.
- (e) Use a cylinder/spool with $r/R > 0.5$ and pull at an angle π , i.e. pulling to the left. Ask the students for the direction of the friction force. Most students think that friction always oppose the motion and will be surprised to see that the demonstration reveals the friction to be to the left as well (in agreement with *Fig. 5*).
- (f) With input from students, derive *Eq. (6)* and the students will realize that friction becomes positive, thus explaining the observation. An important conclusion for the students is that friction contributes to the acceleration of the cylinder in this case.
- (g) Ask the students to investigate whether the friction force might be zero (*Eq. (7)*).
- (h) Show *Fig. 5* to the students. With a few cylinders with different r/R -ratios and using different angles it is easy to demonstrate the direction of the friction force for different regions in the plot.
- (i) Given for instance $r/R = 0.3$, ask the students to calculate the angles for which the friction becomes zero (with this ratio *Eq. (7)* yields $\theta = 127^\circ$ or $\theta = 233^\circ$). With some care this can be demonstrated as well.
- (j) Challenge the students by asking whether it is possible to pull the cylinder without it starting to move. If necessary guide the students to derive *Eq. (10)*.
- (k) With a suitable value for r/R (not too low and not too high) it can be illustrated on the demo setup when pulling at the critical angle θ_c . It will be clear from the demo that the friction force has a direction to compensate for the horizontal component of T . Also, a free body diagram for the situation gives a qualitative explanation why the cylinder does not rotate when pulled at θ_c since the moment of force about the contact point is zero, see *Fig. 7*.

Fig. 7. Cylinder pulled at the critical angle θ_c . In the sketched situation, the pulling force T is fairly close to the critical value given in *Eq. (11)*.

4 SUMMARY

Traditionally, students tend to simplify problems in rigid body dynamics or use their intuition instead of performing a firm analysis by use of the equations of motion. This leads frequently to misconceptions for instance concerning the direction of friction force and the representation of forces in free body diagrams. In this paper, we have discussed how it might be possible to use these misconceptions to create discrepant events and thereby stimulate the students' interest and curiosity at class. It is our hypothesis that this is a way to foster deep learning and develop the engineering skills the students need. Future work will include data collection in terms of pre- and post-tests combined with focus group interviews in order to test this hypothesis.

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